

Twenty five species of Platygastriinae (Hymenoptera: Platygastriidae) new to the fauna of Poland

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.836606>

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ABSTRACT. Twenty five species of Platygastriinae (Hymenoptera: Platygastriidae) new to the fauna of Poland.

New distributional records of 25 species of Platygastriinae (Hymenoptera: Platygastriidae) are given, all reported for the first time from Poland: *Acerotiella boter* (WALKER), *Amblyaspis roboris* (HALIDAY), *A. tritici* (WALKER), *Anopedias tritonus* THOMSON, *Ceratacis cochleata* (WALKER), *Euxestonotus error* (FITCH), *E. hasselbachi* BUHL, *Inostemma hyperici* DEBAUCHE, *Leptacis vlugi* BUHL, *Platygaster acrisius* WALKER, *P. cirsiicola* BUHL et JØRGENSEN, *P. demades* WALKER, *P. dryope* WALKER, *P. henkvlugi* BUHL, *P. hyalinata* (THOMSON), *P. leptines* WALKER, *P. sagana* WALKER, *P. subuliformis* KIEFFER, *P. tisas* WALKER, *Synopeas euryale* (WALKER), *S. gibberosum* BUHL, *S. larides* (WALKER), *S. rhanis* (WALKER), *S. sosis* (WALKER) and *S. subaequale* (FOERSTER). The new records increase the number of Platygastriinae known to occur in Poland to 101 species.

KEY WORDS: Hymenoptera, Platygastroidea, Platygastriidae, Platygastriinae; faunistics, new records, Poland.

INTRODUCTION

GARBARCZYK (1997) listed 56 species of Platygastriidae from Poland, excluding Scelionidae and Sceliotrachelidae, i.e. the Platygastriinae as accepted by most authors today. Later *Synopeas bialowiezaensis* BUHL, 2005 and *Platygaster polonica* BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI, 2016 were described on the basis of specimens known so far only from Poland, and *Inostemma kaponeni* BUHL, 2005 was described from Finland and Poland. In addition, sixteen species were recorded for the first time from Poland by BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI (2016b). Finally, a male of *Synopeas burgeri* BUHL, 2012, a species known so far only from the German female holotype, was discovered in Poland and described (BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI 2016a). This gives a total of 76 species of Platygastriinae recorded from Poland to date. This is still a relatively small number, compared to the 260 platygastriine species known from the British Isles (BUHL & NOTTON 2009) or the ca 220 species from Denmark and Fennoscandia (BUHL 1999). Based on geographical factors and a similar diversity of potential hosts as in better studied areas of central and northern Europe, it has been estimated that the true number of Platygastriinae species in Poland may be at least three times higher than currently known (BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI 2016a). Indeed, a continuation of the recently initiated faunistic survey of Poland yielded another 25 species previously not known from this country; the results are presented below.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

All the specimens listed below were collected by the second author using a sweep net, in large meadows adjacent to mixed (in the lowlands) or mainly spruce (in the mountains) forests. All the voucher specimens are dry-mounted on points and deposited in the collection of the second author, Wrocław, Poland. The previously known distributional data are given after the Hymenoptera Online (<http://hol.osu.edu>) and the personal database of the first author. Data on known hosts, if available, are given after the same sources.

RESULTS

Acerotella boter (WALKER, 1838)

Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland: [XU51] Promno ad Poznań, 01.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, 05.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Eastern Beskidy Mts: [FV08] Ropienka env., 580 m, 27.06.2015, 8 ♀♀.

Bieszczady Mts: [EV96] Baligród (Kiczera), 500 m, 23.06.2015, 1 ♂.

Distribution: British Isles, Scandinavia, Russia.

Amblyaspis roboris (HALIDAY, 1835)

Eastern Beskidy Mts: [FV08] Ropienka env., 580 m, 27.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Distribution: Spain, British Isles, Scandinavia, Baltic countries, Mongolia.

Amblyaspis tritici (WALKER, 1835)

Eastern Beskidy Mts: [FV08] Ropienka env., 580 m, 27.06.2015, 3 ♂♂; [FV07] Zwierzyń ad Lesko, 350 m, 24.06.2015, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂.

Distribution: British Isles, Germany, Scandinavia, Russia, Mongolia.

Anopediastis tritomis THOMSON, 1859

Eastern Beskidy Mts: [FV07] Zwierzyń ad Lesko, 350 m, 24.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Distribution: British Isles, Scandinavia.

Ceratocis cochleata (WALKER, 1835)

Eastern Beskidy Mts: [FV07] Zwierzyń ad Lesko, 350 m, 24.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Distribution: Spain, British Isles, Scandinavia, Baltic countries.

Euxestonotus error (FITCH, 1861)

Eastern Beskidy Mts: [FV08] Ropienka env., 580 m, 27.06.2015, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; [FV07] Zwierzyń ad Lesko, 350 m, 24.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Bieszczady Mts: [EV96] Baligród (Kiczera), 500 m, 23.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Distribution: Holarctic. Host: wheat midge *Sitodiplosis mosellana* (GÉHIN) (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) on wheat.

Euxestonotus hasselbachi* BUHL, 1995*Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland:** [XU51] Promno ad Poznań, 01.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Distribution: British Isles, Netherlands, Germany, Scandinavia, Baltic countries.

Inostemma hyperici* DEBAUCHE, 1947*Eastern Beskidy Mts:** [FV07] Zwierzyń ad Lesko, 350 m, 24.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Distribution: Ireland, Belgium, Scandinavia, Iran.

Leptacis vlugi* BUHL, 1997*Eastern Beskidy Mts:** [FV08] Ropienka env., 580 m, 27.06.2015, 3 ♀♀.

Distribution: Spain, British Isles, Scandinavia, Baltic countries.

Platygaster acrisius* WALKER, 1835*Eastern Beskidy Mts:** [FV08] Ropienka env., 580 m, 27.06.2015, 5 ♀♀.**Bieszczady Mts:** [EV96] Baligród (Kiczera), 500 m, 23.06.2015, 1 ♂, 1 ♀.

Distribution: Spain, British Isles, Scandinavia, Baltic countries.

Platygaster cirsiicola* BUHL et JØRGENSEN, 2011*Eastern Beskidy Mts:** [FV07] Zwierzyń ad Lesko, 350 m, 24.06.2015, 1 ♀.Distribution: Denmark, where this species was reared from the thistle *Cirsium arvense* (L.) (Asteraceae) inhabited by larvae of *Jaapiella cirsiicola* RÜBSAAMEN (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae).***Platygaster demades* WALKER, 1835****Eastern Beskidy Mts:** [FV08] Ropienka env., 580 m, 27.06.2015, 5 ♂♂, 106 ♀♀; [FV07] Zwierzyń ad Lesko, 350 m, 24.06.2015, 5 ♀♀.**Bieszczady Mts:** [EV96] Baligród (Kiczera), 500 m, 23.06.2015, 1 ♂, 4 ♀♀; [EV96] Bystre ad Baligród, 490 m, 28.06.2015, 2 ♀♀.Distribution: Europe, Iran, introduced to North America and New Zealand. Host: chiefly the apple leaf-curling midge *Dasineura mali* KIEFFER (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) on apple trees.***Platygaster dryope* WALKER, 1835****Eastern Beskidy Mts:** [FV08] Ropienka env., 580 m, 27.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Distribution: British Isles, Scandinavia.

Platygaster henkvlugi* BUHL, 1996*Eastern Beskidy Mts:** [FV08] Ropienka env., 580 m, 27.06.2015, 2 ♀♀.**Bieszczady Mts:** [EV96] Baligród (Kiczera), 500 m, 23.06.2015, 3 ♀♀; [EV96] Bystre ad Baligród, 490 m, 28.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Distribution: British Isles, Central Europe, Scandinavia.

Platygaster hyalinata (THOMSON, 1859)**Lower Silesia:** [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, 0.5.06.2015, 1 ♀.**Eastern Beskidy Mts:** [FV08] Ropienka env., 580 m, 27.06.2015, 1 ♀.**Bieszczady Mts:** [EV96] Bystre ad Baligród, 490 m, 28.06.2015, 2 ♀♀.

Distribution: Scandinavia.

Platygaster leptines WALKER, 1835**Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland:** [XU51] Promno ad Poznań, 01.06.2015, 1 ♂.

Distribution: Spain, British Isles, Scandinavia, Baltic countries, Mongolia.

Platygaster sagana WALKER, 1835**Lower Silesia:** [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, 05.06.2015, 2 ♀♀.**Eastern Beskidy Mts:** [FV07] Zwierzyń ad Lesko, 350 m, 24.06.2015, 1 ♀.**Bieszczady Mts:** [EV96] Baligród (Kiczera), 500 m, 23.06.2015, 26 ♀♀.

Distribution: Spain, British Isles, Scandinavia, Germany, Baltic countries, Mongolia, Korea.

Hosts (all cecidomyiid midges): *Rhopalomyia ptarmicae* (VALLOT) on *Achillea ptarmica* L. (Asteraceae); *Rabdophaga albipennis* (LOEW) on *Salix alba* L. (Saliceae); *Contarinia rubicola* KIEFFER on *Rubus fruticosus* L. (Rosaceae); and unidentified cecidomyiids on *Tragopogon pratensis* L. (Asteraceae).***Platygaster subuliformis*** KIEFFER, 1926**Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland:** [XU51] Promno ad Poznań, 01.06.2015, 1 ♀.**Eastern Beskidy Mts:** [FV08] Ropienka env., 580 m, 27.06.2015, 2 ♀♀.Distribution: British Isles, Scandinavia. Host: The *Brassica* pod midge *Dasineura brassicae* WINNERTZ (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae).***Platygaster tisiae*** WALKER, 1835**Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland:** [XU51] Promno ad Poznań, 01.06.2015, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀.**Lower Silesia:** [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, 05.06.2015, 3 ♀♀.

Distribution: Spain, British Isles, Scandinavia, Mongolia.

Synopeas euryale (WALKER, 1835)**Eastern Beskidy Mts:** [FV08] Ropienka env., 580 m, 27.06.2015, 7 ♀♀.Distribution: British Isles, Scandinavia, Baltic countries. Host: *Dasineura leguminicola* (LINTNER) (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) on *Trifolium pratense* L. (Fabaceae). Also reared from the bracket fungus *Meripilus giganteus* (PERS.) (Meripilaceae).***Synopeas gibberosum*** BUHL, 1997**Bieszczady Mts:** [EV96] Bystre ad Baligród, 490 m, 28.06.2015, 1 ♂.

Distribution: British Isles, Scandinavia, Mongolia, Korea.

Synopeas larides (WALKER, 1835)

Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland: [XU51] Promno ad Poznań, 01.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Distribution: British Isles, Germany, Scandinavia, Baltic countries.

Synopeas rhanis (WALKER, 1835)

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, 05.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Distribution: Spain, British Isles, Germany, Scandinavia, Baltic countries, Mongolia, Korea. Host: *Dasineura urticae* (PERRIS) (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) on *Urtica dioica* L. (Urticaceae).

Synopeas sosis (WALKER, 1835)

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, 13.06.2015, 2 ♂♂.

Eastern Beskidy Mts: [FV08] Ropienka env., 580 m, 27.06.2015, 18 ♀♀, 8 ♂♂; [FV07] Zwierzyń ad Lesko, 350 m, 24.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Bieszczady Mts: [EV96] Baligród (Kiczera), 500 m, 23.06.2015, 2 ♂♂.

Distribution: Spain, British Isles, Germany, Scandinavia, Baltic countries, Mongolia. Hosts (all cecidomyiid midges): *Contarinia rubicola* KIEFFER on *Rubus fruticosus* L. (Rosaceae); *Jaapiella veronicae* (VALLOT) on *Veronica longifolia* L. (Veroniceae).

Synopeas subaequale (FOERSTER, 1856)

Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland: [XU51] Promno ad Poznań, 01.06.2015, 1 ♀.

Distribution: Denmark, Germany.

DISCUSSION

Up to the end of the 20th century, fewer than 60 species of Platygastriinae had been recorded from Poland. Compared with the ~260 platygastriine species currently known from the British Isles (BUHL & NOTTON 2009), this number seems very small. The recent revival of microhymenopterous parasitoid research in Poland has yielded new records, including the discovery of a species new to science (BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI 2016). Here, we report on the occurrence of 25 platygastriine species new to the fauna of Poland, which increases the Polish checklist to 101 spp. Some of the old records require verification, however. As all the 25 newly recorded species were collected in just a few localities during rather intermittent trips, further field work and systematic studies are likely to increase this number markedly.

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STRESZCZENIE

Dwadzieścia pięć gatunków Platygastriinae (Hymenoptera: Platygastriidae) nowych dla fauny Polski

Do końca XX wieku mniej niż 60 gatunków błonkówek z podrodziny Platygastriinae (Platygastriidae) zostało wykazanych z terytorium Polski (dla porównania, fauna Wysp Brytyjskich liczy ok. 260 gatunków). Ożywienie badań nad drobnymi błonkoskrzydłymi parazytoidami Polski pozwoliło od tego czasu uzyskać dane na temat występowania kilkunastu kolejnych gatunków, w tym jednego opisanego z okolic Wrocławia jako nowy dla nauki. W niniejszej pracy podane zostały stanowiska występowania kolejnych 25 gatunków, dotychczas nieznanych z naszego kraju: *Acerotella boter* (WALKER), *Amblyaspis roboris* (HALIDAY), *A. tritici* (WALKER), *Anopedias tritomus* THOMSON, *Ceratacis cochleata* (WALKER), *Euxestonotus error* (FITCH), *E. hasselbachi* BUHL, *Inostemma hyperici* DEBAUCHE, *Leptacis vlugi* BUHL, *Platygaster acrisius* WALKER, *P. cirsiicola* BUHL et JØRGENSEN, *P. demades* WALKER, *P. dryope* WALKER, *P. henkvlugi* BUHL, *P. hyalinata* (THOMSON), *P. leptines* WALKER, *P. sagana* WALKER, *P. subuliformis* KIEFFER, *P. tiasis* WALKER, *Synopeas euryale* (WALKER), *S. gibberosum* BUHL, *S. larides* (WALKER), *S. rhanis* (WALKER), *S. sosis* (WALKER) i *S. subaequale* (FOERSTER). Obecnie 101 gatunków Platygastriinae znanych jest z Polski, jednak części gatunków wykazywanych przez starszych autorów nie udało się jak dotychczas ponownie odłowić. Liczba ta z całą pewnością będzie się szybko zmieniać, za czym przemawia fakt, że 25 gatunków podanych w niniejszej pracy zostało odłowionych na zaledwie kilku stanowiskach, w trakcie kilku okazjnych wycieczek terenowych.

Accepted: 24 July 2017; published: 31 July 2017

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